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FUNCTIONS OF LINGUISTIC UNITS IN CREATING AN ARTISTIC IMAGE

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ABSTRACT

Works of fiction are opposed to all other speech works due to the fact that for all of them one of the communicative functions is dominant, namely artistic and aesthetic or poetic. The purpose of this article is to study the linguistic features of a literary text that affect its translation. Accordingly, the following tasks can be distinguished with characterizing a literary text as an object of linguistic analysis and identifying the lexical features of the text that affect the translation.

V.N. Komissarov believes that the main goal of any work of this type is to achieve a certain aesthetic impact, to create an artistic image. Such an aesthetic orientation distinguishes artistic speech from other acts of speech communication, the informative content of which is primary and independent. [1]

After analyzing the translations of literary works, this researcher argues that they are typical deviations from the maximum possible semantic accuracy in order to ensure the artistry of the translation.

According to I.R. Galperin, many texts, and especially literary texts - stories, short stories, novels, plays, folklore works, have an impact on the reader's feelings and excite an aesthetic reaction. The text can evoke images - visual, auditory, tactile and gustatory. These images are not indifferent to the very content of literary and artistic works. [3]

Also I.R. Galperin argues that most texts, from the point of view of their organization, strive to comply with the norms established for a given group of texts (functional styles), and thus, as it were, resist violating the correctness of the text. This, however, does not always apply to literary texts, which, although they obey some generally accepted norms of organization, still retain a significant proportion of the "active unconscious", which often blows up the correctness and affects the nature of the organization of the statement. [4]

T.A. Kazakova [4] in her study identifies several factors related to the literary text: - certain types of sequence, combination or number of language characters. A phonetically or rhythmically justified sequence can, in addition to the meaning of words and the meaning of sentences, evoke certain sensations, semantic mood and associations even before the rational

assimilation of the text. This condition for the creation of a literary text plays a particularly important role in versification. In addition, certain conditions of lexical compatibility can be signs of orderliness, for example, creating such special chains as irony, word play, metaphor or other stylistic devices. Syntactic order is also an unconditional feature of a literary text: from the most complex syntactic structures such as periods in philosophical and psychological prose to jerky or even deliberately violating the norm forms characteristic of "stream of consciousness" prose;

- artistic functions of linguistic signs used for the construction and reconstruction of signs of a literary text in translation. In connection with the text, it is important to take into account not only the actual dictionary meaning of the linguistic signs included in it, but, above all, the artistic functions that these signs can perform in a given text, taking into account the possible differences in literary traditions;

- a certain communicative-pragmatic situation in which a literary text is manifested: the presence of a certain author (with his own cognitive-emotional complex of ideas about the world and about the subject of the statement), the text itself (a work that meets the conditions of artistic ordering) and a reader (with its own cognitive - an emotional complex of ideas about the world), recreating in his mind the subject of the statement.

A.V. Fedorov [1] identifies several features characteristic of a literary text:

- a special, often directly close connection between the artistic image and the linguistic category on the basis of which it is built;

- semantic capacity is manifested in the writer's ability to say more than the direct meaning of words in their totality, to make the reader's thoughts, feelings, and imagination work. The semantic capacity of a literary work is manifested in the forms of realistic typification, either in allegorical allegory, or in the general diversity of artistic speech;

- a pronounced national coloring of content and form, which is quite natural for literature, as for reflecting reality in the images conditioned by it;

- the seal of the time when the work was created - a close connection between the historical situation and the images of the work reflecting it;

- the individual style of the writer uses certain speech styles of the national language. Its unity lends itself to being divided into elements already in the order of stylistic analysis (both the original and the translation in its relation to the original). A special specific area within fiction is poetry, which also has its own genres.

Poetic and prose types are distinguished, which, in turn, are classified according to genre, historical, thematic, chronological and other parameters. Features of poetic texts include:

1) difficulty, "inhibition" of the language of poetry;

2) having your own code;

3) the increased importance of sound organization;

4) complex articulation with a special rhythm, metric;

5) verbal expression: semantic "complication" of the word;

6) the special role of allegories;

7) increased emotionality, etc.

Poetic texts are:

- 1) ultimate emotional and semantic richness;
- 2) tendency to monologue;
- 3) a vivid manifestation of the speech-creative principle;
- 4) expression expression.

Prose is considered as a "continuous" speech, which is characterized by:

- 1) a different rhythm;
- 2) the division of prose texts, due to the semantic and syntactic structure;
- 3) the presence of semantic-logical connections in the presentation.

The following features of prose texts stand out:

- 1) the possibilities of linguistic diversity;
- 2) polyphony;
- 3) attraction to the "constituting" word, "non-emotional" and "non-style";
- 4) wide use of visual and cognitive possibilities of speech.

Thus, our analysis of the characteristics of a literary text shows that a literary text has certain features that distinguish it from other types of texts and make it the most difficult in terms of translation:

- aesthetic impact, creation of an artistic image (V.N. Komissarov, I.R. Galperin);
- deviations from the maximum possible semantic accuracy (V.N. Komissarov);
- certain types of sequence, combination or number of language signs (T.A. Kazakova)
- artistic functions of linguistic signs (T.A. Kazakova);
- a certain communicative-pragmatic situation (T.A. Kazakova);
- close connection between the artistic image and the language category (A.V. Fedorov);
- semantic capacity (A.V. Fedorov);
- national coloring (A.V. Fedorov);
- the seal of that time (A.V. Fedorov);

- individual style of the writer (A.V. Fedorov);
- a large number of phraseological units (V.N. Komissarov);
- variety of lexical and syntactic language means (K. Rice);
- elements of colloquial speech (K. Rice).

Linguistic features are realized in the lexical, grammatical, stylistic features of the text.

It should be noted that the study of linguistic units is a vast field, both special and interdisciplinary research, which cannot be exhausted within the framework of the article. Realizing the incompleteness and limitations of our attempt to characterize the essence of translation and analyze approaches to the linguistic analysis of a literary text, the work done gives us the basis for the following conclusions:

1. A literary text can be regarded as a mechanism arranged in a special way, which contains extremely highly concentrated information. In the artistic style of texts, there may be means of designing aesthetic information, as well as a literary text has certain features that distinguish it from other types of texts. Each performs a specific function, but all serve the same purpose: to saturate the text and fill it with colors in order to maximally involve the reader in the transmitted atmosphere. Also in the article, we can find out that a literary text has such features as: a close connection between the artistic image and the language category, semantic capacity, a pronounced national coloring of content and form, the seal of the time when the work was created, the individual style of the writer.
2. Analyzing the opinions of both Russian and foreign linguists involved in the study

of this problem, we can see that in order to create a full-fledged interlingual translation, a translator must take into account the lexical features of a literary text. In cases where there are no analogues to the constructions of the original

language in the language, an effective way to achieve adequacy is the use of lexical transformations. These transformations help to reflect the main features of a work of art.

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